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Extremely high alkalinity due to dissolution of Mg-rich phyllosilicate in the hemipelagic sediments of the Ulleung Basin (East/Japan Sea): stable Si isotopic evidence and reactive transport modeling

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ABSTRACT

Marine silicate alteration includes the processes of lithogenic silicate (LSi) dissolution, clay formation, and biogenic silica dissolution. LSi dissolution consumes CO₂ and results in marine silicate weathering. Formation of cation-rich clay minerals produces CO₂, which is known as reverse weathering. The net effects on carbon cycling of both processes are poorly constrained as the responsible silicate phases and controlling factors are unclear. We investigate the coupling between LSi dissolution and clay formation by analyzing stable Si isotopic signatures ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}$) of porewater and solid Si phases (reactive LSi, biogenic silica, and amorphous secondary Si phases) in two drill cores from the Ulleung Basin, East/Japan Sea. High porewater total alkalinity (up to 131 meq L⁻¹) was measured, indicating net marine silicate weathering. Based on the elemental composition (Si, K, and Al) as well as $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ of the reactive LSi phase in sediments, phyllosilicates that are potentially mica group silicates are identified as the primary silicate group that sustains marine silicate weathering in the Ulleung Basin. Our reactive transport modeling supports such an inference and further reveals how early diagenetic reactions could affect the downcore occurrence and rates of LSi dissolution and clay formation. Predominant clay formation/reverse weathering in sulfate-reducing sediments is evident from the high $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ values in porewater. In the shallow methanogenesis zone, net marine silicate weathering due to phyllosilicate dissolution explains the observed high total alkalinity and low $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ in porewater. Nonetheless, we show that the rates of clay formation primarily control the level of porewater total alkalinity, even in the condition of net marine silicate weathering. Clay formation is strongly suppressed by the low porewater pH as a result of the active fermentation in the site with the highest rate of organic matter degradation. Deep in the methanogenesis zone, enrichment of dissolved aluminum from LSi dissolution counteracts the influence of pH on silicate alteration processes, thereby further limiting the extent of LSi dissolution, as supported by the downcore increasing of porewater $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$. Our results demonstrate that $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ in porewater reflects downcore variations in marine silicate alteration, with microbial processes and dissolved aluminum accumulation regulating the rates of LSi dissolution and clay formation.

1. Introduction

Early diagenesis in marine sediments affects the cycling and origin of particulate and dissolved carbon (Berner et al., 1983; Arndt et al., 2013; Sun and Turchyn, 2014; Swart, 2015; Fantle et al., 2020; Jørgensen et al., 2022). Besides carbonate diagenesis, studies have demonstrated that marine silicate alteration, including lithogenic silicate (LSi)

dissolution (or marine silicate weathering), clay formation (or reverse weathering), and biogenic silica (BSi) dissolution, has the potential to regulate carbon dioxide (CO₂) and pH in porewaters through the following equations (Mackenzie and Garrels, 1966; Wallmann et al., 2008, 2023; Isson and Planavsky, 2018; Isson et al., 2020; Torres et al., 2020; Warr, 2022; Baldermann et al., 2025; Farkas et al., 2025; Hong et al., 2025):

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LSi dissolution/marine silicate weathering:

Clay formation/reverse weathering:

BSi dissolution:

Marine silicate alteration (Eq. (1) + Eq. (2) + Eq. (3)):

where \mathbf{a}_1 to \mathbf{a}_3 , \mathbf{b}_1 to \mathbf{b}_3 , and \mathbf{c}_2 are the stoichiometric coefficients determined by the type of reactive silicate phases that dissolve or precipitate. Previous studies have emphasized the presence and impact of LSi dissolution/clay formation on the climate and elemental cycles (Mackenzie and Kump, 1995; Michalopoulos and Aller, 1995, 2004; Wallmann et al., 2008, 2023; Solomon et al., 2014; Ehlert et al., 2016; Kim et al., 2016; Sample et al., 2017; Isson and Planavsky, 2018; Trower and Fischer, 2019; Geilert et al., 2020, 2023, 2024; Krissansen-Totton and Catling, 2020; Luo et al., 2023; Rahman and Trower, 2023). The global net CO₂ production and consumption through marine silicate alteration ($\mathbf{a}_1 - \mathbf{b}_1$ in Eq. (4)) have been estimated to be 1–4 T mol C yr⁻¹ (Torres et al., 2020) and 0.5–10 T mol C yr⁻¹ (Isson et al., 2020), respectively. These estimates are associated with high uncertainties due to the poorly constrained silicate reactants and products (i.e. Lithogenic silicate and Neoformed clay in Eq. (4)) that determine the stoichiometry of the CO₂ and bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) ($\mathbf{a}_1 - \mathbf{b}_1$ in Eq. (4)). For instance, Isson and Planavsky (2018) demonstrated that forming different types of clays varies in CO₂ production by a factor of five. A recent review by Hong et al. (2025) showed that types of LSi and neoformed clay involved in marine silicate alteration affect the porewater carbonate alkalinity and major cation composition under identical diagenetic conditions. Various types of LSi have been proposed to dissolve and result in marine silicate weathering. For example, dissolution of feldspar is suggested by Wallmann et al. (2008) since they found increased sodium (Na⁺) concentrations in porewater and decreased Na as well as calcium (Ca) contents in bulk sediments. Numerical modeling demonstrated that vermiculite and chlorite are able to dissolve and release cations such as magnesium (Mg²⁺) and potassium (K⁺) to porewater in drill core retrieved from the Peru-Chile Trench (Meister et al. 2022). Dissolution of clay minerals such as smectite or illite driven by microbes has been observed in multiple studies through approaches such as X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning transmission electron microscopy (Vorhies and Gaines, 2009; Liu et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2019; Köster et al., 2021; Jung et al., 2022). These different reactive LSi phases that undergo alteration could have profound effects on the speciation of dissolved inorganic carbon and the saturation state of authigenic carbonate in marine sediment (Sun and Turchyn, 2014).

The rate of marine silicate alteration also determines the amounts of CO₂ produced and consumed. Factors such as pH, dissolved aluminum (DAI), and dissolved silicon (DSi) concentrations in porewater can potentially affect the rates of LSi dissolution and clay formation (Oelkers et al., 1994; Nagy, 1995; Pokrovsky and Schott, 2000; Tosca et al., 2016). The effect of pH has been particularly highlighted. Studies have shown that dissolution rates of forsterite, wollastonite, and lizardite are significantly affected by soil pH ranging from 3 to 8 (Palandri and Kharaka, 2004; Haque et al., 2023). A laboratory precipitation experiment conducted by Tosca et al. (2016) found that greenalite precipitation is highly sensitive to pH, with rates increasing by a factor of 1.7

across a pH range of 7.7 to 8.3. It is however challenging to study the effect of pH due to the complicated feedback between marine silicate alteration and other biogeochemical reactions in marine sediments. To this aim, reactive transport modeling considering ion speciation, reaction kinetics, and thermodynamics (Boudreau, 1997; Steefel et al., 2005; Hong et al., 2014) serves as a promising tool for quantitatively understanding the governing factors, including pH, that affect the rate of marine silicate alteration.

The goal of this paper is to determine 1) the type of reactive LSi phases involved in marine silicate alteration and 2) the factors affecting the rates of marine silicate alteration. Active marine silicate weathering as a result of net LSi dissolution from the Ulleung Basin was previously inferred from the high porewater total alkalinity (TA) that is 30 to 60 times higher than the seawater value (ca. 2 meq L⁻¹) (Fig. 1) (Kim et al., 2016). The sediment cores from two sites in the Ulleung Basin were leached sequentially to separate the different Si phases, following an improved protocol based on our previous work (Huang et al., 2023). The elemental composition and stable Si isotopic composition ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}$) of the different Si phases were analyzed to constrain the silicate types involved in LSi dissolution. The interplay between marine silicate alteration and other early diagenetic reactions is investigated by downcore solute concentrations and $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ of porewater, together with rates of mineral and microbial processes quantified through reactive transport modeling.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study site

The Ulleung Basin is a back-arc basin located in the southwestern East/Japan Sea (Fig. 1). The central basin has water depths of ca. 2000 m with two continental slopes connected to the west and south sides of the basin (Fig. 1). To investigate gas hydrate distribution inside the Ulleung Basin, ten drill cores were retrieved during the Second Ulleung Basin Gas Hydrate Drilling Expedition in 2010 (UBGH2; Fig. 1) (Ryu et al., 2013). Site UBGH 2-1_1 (2-1_1 hereafter), with maximum porewater TA of 131 meq L⁻¹, is located in the southwestern flank of the basin with a water depth of 1534 m (Fig. 1). The sediments of 2-1_1 are mainly hemipelagic with periodic mud-clasts and tephra layers (Ryu et al., 2013; Bahk et al., 2016). Site UBGH 2-6 (2-6 hereafter), with maximum porewater TA of 75 meq L⁻¹, is located in the northern part of the basin with a water depth of 2153 m (Fig. 1). The sediments at depths between 0 and 110 m below seafloor (mbsf) are mainly hemipelagic mud interbedded with turbidite. Frequent occurrence of turbidite was observed between 110 and 210 mbsf (Bahk et al., 2013; Ryu et al., 2013). No gas hydrate was found in 2-1_1, whereas the presence of gas hydrate was observed at around 150 mbsf in 2-6 (Bahk et al., 2013; Ryu et al., 2013). Mica, albite, K-feldspar, and quartz are the most abundant primary silicates, while illite is the most abundant secondary silicate in the sediments of both sites (Lee et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2016; Huang et al., 2023). Abundant siliceous organisms, such as diatom frustules, were found through microscopic observations (Bahk et al., 2013).

2.2. A revised sequential leaching protocol for solid phase separation

Sediments after porewater squeezing were used for leaching. These sediments have been stored under a 4 °C condition since 2010. A modified sequential leaching protocol (H25 protocol, hereafter), adapted from our previous work (H23 protocol, hereafter) (Huang et al., 2023), was employed to enhance the separation of diagenetically altered BSi and LSi. The procedure of the modified protocol is described in Supplementary Material 1 and Table S1. Briefly, all sediments were treated sequentially by HCl, Na₂CO₃, and NaOH solutions at variable temperatures depending on the step (Table S1). The entire leachates were collected with fresh leaching solution replenished at each time point to improve leaching efficiency in the H25 protocol (Table S1). An additional 1-hour 1 M NaOH leaching step was added after Na₂CO₃

Fig. 1. The left panel shows the locations of the East/Japan Sea, while the right panel shows the location of the Ulleung Basin. Red stars indicate the drilling cores recovered from the UBGH2 Expedition with the two study sites, 2-6 and 2-1_1, highlighted. Black stars are the sites drilled during Deep Sea Drilling Project Leg. 31 (White, 1975) and International Ocean Discovery Program Expedition 346 (Tada et al., 2015). Symbol size refers to the maximum porewater total alkalinity at each site. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

leaching in the H25 protocol to dissolve remaining BSi, if any (Table S1).

2.3. Geochemical analyses of porewater and leachate

The pH and concentrations of porewater species (TA, sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), ammonium (NH_4^+), Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , K^+ , DSI, and Cl^-) were reported by Kim et al. (2016) and are included in Table S1. The concentrations of dissolved organic carbon (DOC) were analyzed using the method described by Ryu et al. (2012) and are reported in this study (Table S2).

Concentrations of Si, Al, Fe, Mg, Ca, and K in leachates and total Al concentrations in porewater (colloidal Al and DAI passed the 0.2 μm filters during porewater squeezing; Moran and Moore, 1989; Pokrovsky et al., 2006) were measured using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES; iCAP 6000 series, Thermo Fisher Scientific) at the Department of Geological Sciences, Stockholm University. The measured elemental contents of leachates were corrected for background contribution by subtracting the elemental contents in blank leaching solutions. The international (NIST 1634f and SLRS-6) and in-house standards were measured to evaluate the analysis performance. The concentrations of total Al in porewater and elements in leachate are reported in Tables S2 and S3, respectively. For the porewater samples from 2-6, total Al concentrations were below the detection limit (ca. 0.1 μM). Therefore, they are not discussed in the following section.

Five out of 27 porewater samples with SO_4^{2-} concentrations greater than 1 mM were treated with the magnesium-induced co-precipitation (MAGIC) method (Georg et al., 2006) to separate DSI from porewater matrix. Before applying the MAGIC method, DOC was removed by adding 10 μL of 30 % (vol vol⁻¹) hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) to the porewater samples. After an overnight reaction at room temperature, H_2O_2 was removed from the samples by heating to 50 °C with a water bath until the bubbling ceased. The MAGIC method includes three rounds of co-precipitation. For the first round, 40 μL of 4 M NaOH was added to 1 ml samples for 1 h of co-precipitation. The supernatant and precipitate were separated through centrifugation (10,000 rpm for 10 min). Another 40 μL of 4 M NaOH was added to the supernatant for another hour of co-precipitation. The supernatant and precipitate were again separated with centrifugation. For the final round of co-precipitation, ca. 5 mg of extra magnesium chloride (BioXtra grades, Sigma-Aldrich) was added to the supernatant to induce more brucite co-precipitation and increase DSI recovery before adding 40 μL of 4 M NaOH to the supernatant for 1 h of reaction. Supernatant and precipitate were separated and collected afterward. All collected precipitates from the

three steps were washed with deionized water and then dissolved in 2 ml of 1 M HCl. To check for Si recovery, DSI concentrations of supernatant were measured following the molybdate-blue spectrophotometric protocol (Pettersson and Karlberg, 1999) with a spectrophotometer (810 nm; Evolution 260 BIO, Thermo Scientific) in the Department of Geological Sciences, Stockholm University. Overall, the Si recovery by MAGIC treatment was between 95 and 99 % for the five treated porewater samples.

Porewater (with and without MAGIC treatment) and leachates were passed through cation exchange columns (Bio-Rad AG®50 W-X12) to remove cations, as described in Huang et al. (2023). The Si recovery after column purification was better than 97 % (97 to 101 %; $n = 232$).

Stable Si isotopic compositions, including ^{28}Si , ^{29}Si , and ^{30}Si of porewater and leachates samples, were measured using a multicollector-inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (Nu Plasma II MC-ICP-MS, Nu Instruments Ltd.) at the Vegacenter, Swedish Museum of Natural History, Sweden. The samples were introduced into the MC-ICP-MS through an ESI Apex HF desolvating nebulizer ($\sim 100 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ uptake rate). Samples and standards (Diatomite, IRMM-018, and Big Batch) were all doped with Li before measurement (Sun et al., 2018). The Si isotopic values are reported as $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$:

$$\delta^{30}\text{Si} = (R_{\text{Sample}}/R_{\text{Standard}} - 1) \times 1000 \quad (5)$$

R_{Sample} and R_{Standard} are the $^{30}\text{Si}/^{28}\text{Si}$ ratios of sample and standard (NBS 28). The analyses were conducted in five sessions. The quality of measurement was assessed by the $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ values of standards and mass-dependent fractionation between $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ and $\delta^{29}\text{Si}$ conducted in each session. The $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ values of Diatomite, IRMM-018, and Big Batch agree with the published values (Table S4) (Reynolds et al., 2007; Hendry et al., 2011). Uncertainties are reported as 2SD of replicates, and uncertainties of unknowns are propagated to include long-term uncertainty of Diatomite. The slope of the mass-dependent fractionation also agrees with the published values (Table S4) (Reynolds et al., 2007). The $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ of porewater and leachates are reported in Tables S2 and S3, respectively.

2.4. Numerical model setup

2.4.1. Solute transport network

We used Crunchflow, a multiple-component reactive transport modeling package, for the simulation (Steeffel et al., 2015). The general

equation of the model for any target chemical species i is as follows:

$$\frac{\partial (C_i)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \left(D \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial x} \right)}{\partial x} + R_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (6)$$

where C_i is the concentration of the target species (mol kg^{-1}), t is time (second), x is downcore depth (m), D is the effective diffusion/dispersion coefficient ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) in the porous media, R_i is the reaction rates that are relevant to species i , and n is the total porewater species ($n = 29$). A total of 19 primary species and 10 secondary species were included in this model and are described in [Supplementary Material 2](#). The effective diffusion coefficients were calculated according to the Archie's Law ([Archie, 1947; Delgado, 2006](#)):

$$D = D_o \varphi^{1.5} \quad (7)$$

D_o is the diffusion coefficient in pure water at 25 °C from [Boudreau \(1997\)](#), and φ is porosity with a constant value of 0.7 assigned in the modeling. The exponent of 1.5 is the cementation exponent to account for tortuosity. Solute diffusion serves as an important constraint for how long the model should be executed, which is 70 kyrs. Such a timescale was determined based on the fitting of measured solute concentrations (TA, SO_4^{2-} , NH_4^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , K^+ , and DSi) of 2-1_1 and 2-6. For DAL, we considered only labile Al^{3+} , not taking into account the intricate details of Al speciation or its interactions with natural organic and inorganic ligands in our modeling. ([Campbell et al., 1983; Driscoll and Schecher, 1990](#)). Thus, the modeled porewater DAL concentrations are not directly comparable to the measured porewater total Al concentrations ([Section 2.3](#)). We note that the selected timescale represents the temporal duration required to fit the observed porewater profiles given the assigned reaction network (see later). As we did not consider sedimentation in the current modeling due to the potential numerical error from CrunchFlow ([Hong et al., 2016](#)), the selected timescale is thus only first-order accurate. Also, we did not consider advection in the current model as compaction-induced advection is trivial compared to diffusion for all ions considered for the two investigated sites ([Hong et al., 2014](#)). External fluid advection was also not considered in the model as it was concluded to be insignificant in the basin flank, where our study sites are located ([Kim et al., 2013](#)).

Acid-base, mineral, and microbial-mediated reactions were included in our model. The acid-base reactions are described in [Supplementary Material 2](#) and [Table S5a](#). Based on previous XRD findings ([Huang et al., 2023](#)), we modeled the saturation of (1) albite (representing plagioclase), (2) phlogopite and vermiculite (representing mica group silicate), (3) montmorillonite and saponite (representing smectite group silicate), (4) microcline (representing K-feldspar), (5) clinocllore (representing chlorite group silicate), (6) quartz, and (7) opal (representing BSi). Their formula and stoichiometric factors are listed in [Table S5b](#). Following the modeled saturation ([Section 3.3.1](#)), six silicate phases, albite, phlogopite, vermiculite, montmorillonite, saponite, and opal, were simulated for their release and uptake of DSi as well as cations ([Table 1](#)). Pyrite and calcite precipitation/dissolution were included in the model, as they are crucial to regulating porewater TA and pH ([Reimers et al., 1996; Snyder et al., 2007; Hong et al., 2014](#)). The rates of selected minerals and opal were modeled according to the transition state theory (TST) ([Lasaga, 1984](#)). The detailed rate expressions of TST are described in [Supplementary Material 3](#). Due to the apparent caveat in our selected timescale, we mostly focus on the temporal changes in reaction rates and porewater profiles instead of the absolute rates that may be dependent on the selected modeling time scale.

Seven microbial processes were considered in our model following a similar reaction network as in [Hong et al. \(2025\)](#): organic matter hydrolysis, fermentation, acetotrophic methanogenesis, hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis, hydrogenotrophic sulfate reduction, acetotrophic sulfate reduction, and anaerobic oxidation of methane. Full equations and stoichiometric factors are listed in [Table 1](#). For organic matter

Table 1

Equations and stoichiometric factors of the mineral/opal and microbial reactions were considered.

Mineral/opal Reaction	Equation
Albite	$\text{NaAlSi}_3\text{O}_8(\text{s}) + 4\text{H}^+ + 4\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{aq}) \rightarrow \text{Na}^+ + \text{Al}^{3+} + 3\text{H}_4\text{SiO}_4(\text{aq})$
Phlogopite	$\text{KMg}_3(\text{AlSi}_3\text{O}_{10})(\text{OH})_2(\text{s}) + 10\text{H}^+ \rightarrow \text{K}^+ + 3\text{Mg}^{2+} + \text{Al}^{3+} + 3\text{H}_4\text{SiO}_4(\text{aq})$
Vermiculite	$\text{Mg}_{3.43}(\text{Al}_{0.86}\text{Si}_{3.14}\text{O}_{10})(\text{OH})_2(\text{s}) + 9.44\text{H}^+ + 0.56\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{aq}) \rightarrow 3.43\text{Mg}^{2+} + 0.86\text{Al}^{3+} + 3.14\text{H}_4\text{SiO}_4(\text{aq})$
Montmorillonite	$\text{K}_{0.34}\text{Mg}_{0.34}(\text{Al}_{1.66}\text{Si}_4\text{O}_{10})(\text{OH})_2(\text{s}) + 6\text{H}^+ + 4\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 0.34\text{K}^+ + 0.34\text{Mg}^{2+} + 1.66\text{Al}^{3+} + 4\text{H}_4\text{SiO}_4(\text{aq})$
Saponite	$\text{K}_{0.34}\text{Mg}_3(\text{Al}_{0.34}\text{Si}_{3.66}\text{O}_{10})(\text{OH})_2(\text{s}) + 7.36\text{H}^+ + 2.64\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 0.34\text{K}^+ + 3\text{Mg}^{2+} + 0.34\text{Al}^{3+} + 3.66\text{H}_4\text{SiO}_4(\text{aq})$
Opal (representing BSi)	$\text{SiO}_2(\text{am}) + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_4\text{SiO}_4(\text{aq})$
Microbial Process	Equation
Organic matter hydrolysis	$(\text{CH}_2\text{O})(\text{NH}_3)_{0.1111}(\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4)_{0.009434(\text{s})} + 0.092242\text{H}^+ \rightarrow 0.166666667\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6(\text{aq}) + 0.1111\text{NH}_4^+ + 0.009434\text{HPO}_4^{2-}$
Fermentation	$0.041667\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6(\text{aq}) + 0.166666667\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{aq}) \rightarrow 0.0833333\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^- + 0.166666667\text{H}_2(\text{aq}) + 0.166666667\text{H}^+ + 0.08333334\text{HCO}_3^-$
Hydrogenotrophic sulfate reduction	$0.5\text{H}_2(\text{aq}) + 0.125\text{SO}_4^{2-} + 0.125\text{H}^+ \rightarrow 0.125\text{HS}^- + 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{aq})$
Acetotrophic sulfate reduction	$0.125\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^- + 0.125\text{SO}_4^{2-} \rightarrow 0.125\text{HS}^- + 0.25\text{HCO}_3^-$
Anaerobic oxidation of methane	$0.125\text{CH}_4(\text{aq}) + 0.375\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{aq}) \rightarrow 0.5\text{H}_2(\text{aq}) + 0.125\text{HCO}_3^- + 0.125\text{H}^+$
Hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis	$0.5\text{H}_2(\text{aq}) + 0.125\text{HCO}_3^- + 0.125\text{H}^+ \rightarrow 0.125\text{CH}_4(\text{aq}) + 0.375\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{aq})$
Acetotrophic methanogenesis	$0.125\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^- + 0.125\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{aq}) \rightarrow 0.125\text{CH}_4(\text{aq}) + 0.125\text{HCO}_3^-$

hydrolysis, we assumed a far-from-equilibrium condition. Thus, its rate depends entirely on the assigned kinetic constants that are determined by fitting modeling results with the measured NH_4^+ profiles (best-fit scenario) or varied for the different sensitivity test scenarios (see later). Except for organic matter hydrolysis, the equilibrium constants of microbial processes were calculated according to the standard Gibbs free energy yield compiled by [Benjamin \(2014\)](#). The Monod equation was used to express the rate of microbial processes (except for organic matter hydrolysis). A detailed description of the Monod expression is shown in [Supplementary Material 4](#).

Our modeling approach for organic matter degradation is different from previous modeling efforts (e.g. [Wallmann et al., 2006; Sauer et al., 2021](#)) in that we prescribed in detail the reaction network so that the activity of proton (i.e. pH) can be calculated explicitly by the model. For example, methanogenesis was often prescribed as a fraction of the overall organic matter degradation (e.g. [Wallmann et al., 2006; Sauer et al., 2021](#)). This is only adequate when carbon turnover is the sole focus, which was the case for the aforementioned studies. However, this approach lacks the ability to account for pH correctly and thus cannot be used to study how pH as a control for marine silicate alteration.

Cation exchange was considered to account for dissolved cations replacing the existing cations from clay surfaces. The selectivity coefficients between NH_4^+ and cations (Ca^{2+} , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , and Na^+) during the ion adsorption on the neoformed montmorillonite were derived from [Boatman and Murray \(1982\)](#) and are listed in [Table S5i](#).

2.4.2. Model framework and scenarios

The physical dimension of the model includes a total of 280 1-meter blocks to match the dimensions of the two drill cores investigated. Porewater compositions and pH at the upper boundary were derived from measured values of the topmost porewater samples of 2-1_1 and 2-6 ([Table S5g](#)) ([Kim et al., 2016](#)). The sediment temperature across the sediment-water interface was set to be 0.2 °C, and the temperature gradient was set to be 0.1 °C m^{-1} , based on the measurements from 2-1_1

(Lee et al., 2013). We used extra layers of sediment (62 1-meter blocks) with lower porewater Mg^{2+} and K^+ concentrations and higher Ca^{2+} concentrations than those of the cored depth to simulate measured Mg^{2+} , K^+ , and Ca^{2+} concentrations in the bottom part of the drill core (Kim et al., 2016) (Table S5h). The lower boundary was set as a no-flux boundary. This can be justified by the insignificant fluid flow, as concluded previously (Kim et al., 2013). As there were no iron (oxyhydr) oxide phases considered in the current model, we added an additional Fe^{2+} source in the entire simulation depth so that pyrite precipitation, an important reaction for porewater pH and TA, can be better accounted for (Table S5g).

Three sensitivity test scenarios, *Core 1*, *Core 1_{low org}*, and *Core 1_{low org} + CH₄*, were modeled for 2-1_1. *Core 1* is the best-fit scenario for the measured porewater solute profiles of 2-1_1. The subscript “low org” refers to an assigned 1.4 times lower kinetic constant for organic matter hydrolysis as compared to *Core 1* (Table 2). The subscript “CH₄” refers to an external methane source assigned for this as compared to *Core 1* (Table 2). Two scenarios, *Core 6* and *Core 6_{kmica}* were modeled for 2-6. *Core 6* is the best-fit scenario for the measured porewater solute profiles of 2-6. The subscript “kmica” refers to different kinetic constants for mica group silicates, with higher values for phlogopite and lower values for vermiculite used in comparison to those in *Core 6* (Table 2). An external methane source was assigned in both *Core 6* and *Core 6_{kmica}* to simulate the high methane flux observed from 2-6, which sustains the gas hydrate deposits at this site (Table 2). A kinetic constant for organic matter hydrolysis that is 2.2 times lower than that for *Core 1* was used for both *Core 6* and *Core 6_{kmica}* (Table 2). Lower cation exchange capacities of montmorillonite were assigned in *Core 6* and *Core 6_{kmica}* than the capacities in the other three 2-1_1 scenarios to match the measured NH_4^+ profile in 2-6 (Table S5i).

To relate marine silicate alteration with alkalinity, we report DSi, total cation (Σ cation), and HCO_3^- contributions by marine silicate alteration, which were quantified by comparing the changes in abundance of the altered silicate phases (LSi, Neofomed clay, and BSi) between the initial condition and model results at 70 kyr. Detailed calculations are given in Supplementary Material 5.

3. Results

3.1. Si content, $\delta^{30}Si$ value, Si/Al, and Si/K of porewater and leachate

The composition of HCl and Na_2CO_3 leachates from the modified protocol (i.e. H25 protocol) are similar to those from the leachates derived by the H23 protocol. On the other hand, the composition of 4 M NaOH (NaOH, hereafter) leachates is quite different between the two protocols. In general, the NaOH leachates derived by the H23 protocol have at least two times higher Si contents and ratios of Si/Al and Si/K as compared to those derived by the H25 protocol. The $\delta^{30}Si$ values are at least 0.5 ‰ higher in NaOH leachates from the H23 protocol compared to those from the H25 protocol (Fig. S1; Table S6). When examining the leachates from both protocols, the two investigated sites have similar elemental contents, $\delta^{30}Si$ values, as well as Si/Al and Si/K ratios, except for the $\delta^{30}Si$ values of HCl leachates. The $\delta^{30}Si$ values of HCl leachates

from the H23 protocol are about 0.8 ‰ lower in 2-1_1 than in 2-6 (Table S6d). Detailed documentation on the measured results of leachates and the discussion on the Si phase representative of leachate are provided in Table S6 and Supplementary Material 6, respectively.

Compared to all leachates, Si/Al ratios in porewater of 2-1_1 are the highest (no Si/Al ratio in porewater of 2-6 is available; Fig. S1b). The Si/K ratios in porewater are the lowest among all leachates (Table S6c). The two study sites have similar $\delta^{30}Si$ values of porewater ($\delta^{30}Si_{pw}$) with a larger range in 2-1_1 (−0.6 to 1.2 ‰) than that in 2-6 (−0.1 to 0.8 ‰) (Figs. S1a and S1c).

3.2. Downcore porewater solute concentrations and $\delta^{30}Si$

The DSi and cation concentrations (K^+ , Mg^{2+} , and NH_4^+) between the two sites were normalized with Cl^- concentrations to account for fluids affected by freshening (Kim et al., 2013). Three zones are identified based on downcore DSi/ Cl^- and $\delta^{30}Si_{pw}$ (Figs. 2a, 2b, 2e, and 2f).

3.2.1. Zone 1

From 0 to 10 mbsf for 2-1_1 and 0 to 20 mbsf for 2-6, the highest $\delta^{30}Si_{pw}$ values (up to 0.4 ‰), accompanied by the lowest DSi/ Cl^- , were observed in this zone (Figs. 2a, 2b, 2e, and 2f). For both sites, increases in TA and ratios of NH_4^+/Cl^- , K^+/Cl^- , and Mg^{2+}/Cl^- , as well as a decrease in SO_4^{2-} concentrations with depth, were found in this zone (Fig. 2). TA are higher in 2-1_1 than those in 2-6, while no significant differences in SO_4^{2-} concentrations and ratios of K^+/Cl^- , Mg^{2+}/Cl^- , and NH_4^+/Cl^- between the sites were observed (Fig. 2).

3.2.2. Zone 2

A decrease in $\delta^{30}Si_{pw}$ values and an increase in DSi/ Cl^- ratios with depth were observed from 10 to 40 mbsf for 2-1_1 and from 20 to 65 mbsf for 2-6 (Figs. 2a, 2b, 2e, and 2f). The $\delta^{30}Si_{pw}$ values are lower in 2-1_1 (−0.6 to −0.3 ‰) as compared to those in 2-6 (−0.1 to 0.1 ‰) (Figs. 2b and 2f), while DSi/ Cl^- ratios are similar between the two sites (Fig. 2). TA, as well as ratios of K^+/Cl^- and NH_4^+/Cl^- increase with depth at both sites (Fig. 2). The Mg^{2+}/Cl^- ratios increase with depth in 2-1_1 and decrease with depth in 2-6 (Figs. 2d and 2h). TA and ratios of Mg^{2+}/Cl^- and NH_4^+/Cl^- are higher in 2-1_1 as compared to those in 2-6, and K^+/Cl^- ratios are similar at both sites (Fig. 2).

3.2.3. Zone 3

The gradual increases of both DSi/ Cl^- ratios and $\delta^{30}Si_{pw}$ values (from 0.1 to 1.2 ‰) were observed from 40 to 207 mbsf for 2-1_1 and from 65 to 207 mbsf for 2-6 (Figs. 2a, 2b, 2e, and 2f). $\delta^{30}Si_{pw}$ values and DSi/ Cl^- ratios are comparable between the two sites (Figs. 2a, 2b, 2e, and 2f). TA and K^+/Cl^- ratios increase from the top of Zone 3 to ca. 150 mbsf followed by a decrease to the core bottom at both sites (Figs. 2a, 2d, 2e, and 2h). Mg^{2+}/Cl^- ratios in 2-1_1 increase from the top of Zone 3 to ca. 80 mbsf followed by a decrease to the core bottom (Fig. 2d). 2-6 shows a decrease in Mg^{2+}/Cl^- ratios with depth in this zone (Fig. 2h). An increase in NH_4^+/Cl^- ratios with depth was observed in this zone for both sites (Figs. 2c and 2g). NH_4^+/Cl^- ratios are higher in 2-1_1 above 150 mbsf but lower below 150 mbsf as compared to those from the same

Table 2

Key parameters for the model sensitivity tests.

Simulation Scenario	Kinetic constants of organic matter hydrolysis*	Kinetic constants of phlogopite/vermiculite*	External methane source
<i>Core 1</i>	−10.00	−10.76/−10.89	No
<i>Core 1_{low org}</i>	−10.15		No
<i>Core 1_{low org} + CH₄</i>	−10.15		Yes
<i>Core 6_{kmica}</i>	−10.35		Yes
<i>Core 6</i>	−10.35	−10.75/−10.90	Yes

*log₁₀ value with a unit of mol m^{−2} s^{−1}.

Fig. 2. (a) & (e) Profiles of porewater DSi/Cl⁻ (black circle) and TA (dark red bar). (b) & (f) Profiles of $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ of porewater and separated Si phases. (c) & (g) Profiles of porewater SO_4^{2-} (red diamond) and $\text{NH}_4^+/\text{Cl}^-$ (black star). (d) & (h) Profiles of K^+/Cl^- (blue circle) and $\text{Mg}^{2+}/\text{Cl}^-$ (black star). Results of porewater species (TA and concentrations of DSi, cations, Cl^- , and SO_4^{2-}) are from Kim et al. (2016). Corresponding zones defined by DSi/Cl⁻ and $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ were also indicated by the grey dash lines. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

depth range in 2-6 (Figs. 2c and 2g). Similar K^+/Cl^- ratios were found at both sites, while TA and $\text{Mg}^{2+}/\text{Cl}^-$ ratios are higher in 2-1_1 than those in 2-6 (Figs. 2a, 2d, 2e, and 2h).

3.2.4. $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ of separated Si phases

Following the discussion in Supplementary Material 6 and our previous study (Huang et al., 2023), we suggest that the representative composition for amorphous secondary Si phases (ASSi; i.e. metal (hydroxy)oxide and clay-like material with Si adsorbed on or incorporated into it), reactive LSi, and BSi can be derived from the following leaching steps.

- ASSi: HCl 13 hr leachates reported from the H23 protocol
- BSi: Na_2CO_3 5 hr leachates reported from the H23 protocol
- Reactive LSi: NaOH 4 hr leachates from the H25 protocol

We note here that this is a location-specific result, specifically tuned for the sediments from the Ulleung Basin.

Downcore $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ of ASSi ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{ASSi}}$) changes follow a similar pattern as that for $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ in Zones 1 and 2 (Figs. 2b and 2f). No noticeable downcore change in $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{ASSi}}$ was seen in Zone 3 for both sites (Figs. 2b and 2f). Lower $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{ASSi}}$ values with a broader range can be observed in

2-1_1 than those in 2-6 (Figs. 2b and 2f). Downcore $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ of BSi ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{BSi}}$) and LSi ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{LSi}}$) are less variable and substantially different from the profiles of $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ and $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{ASSi}}$ (Figs. 2b and 2f).

3.3. Model results

3.3.1. Porewater profile and saturation of Si phases

The best-fit model scenarios *Core 1* and *Core 6* match the measured porewater profiles from 2-1_1 and 2-6, respectively (Fig. 3). Compared to *Core 1*, scenarios *Core 1_{low org}*, and *Core 1_{low org} + CH₄* predict lower TA, Mg^{2+} , and K^+ concentrations due to the lower kinetic constants assigned for organic matter hydrolysis (Fig. 3a; Table 2). Model scenarios *Core 6_{kmica}* and *Core 6* have similar downcore TA and NH_4^+ profiles due to identical kinetic constants of organic matter hydrolysis assigned (Fig. 3b; Table 2). *Core 6_{kmica}* has lower K^+ concentrations but higher Mg^{2+} concentrations (up to 1.5 mM) than those in *Core 6*, which is due to the different kinetic constants of phlogopite and vermiculite assigned to these two scenarios (Fig. 3b; Table 2).

Modeled saturation index for silicate minerals and BSi at 70 kyr indicates that quartz, microcline, saponite, clinocllore, and montmorillonite are oversaturated, while albite, phlogopite, vermiculite, and BSi are undersaturated in all scenarios (Fig. S2). No apparent difference in

Fig. 3. Profiles of TA, K^+ , Mg^{2+} , NH_4^+ , and DSI concentrations from measurements and model scenarios for (a) 2-1_1 and (b) 2-6. Solid circles indicate porewater measurements.

Fig. 4. Average releases and uptakes of DSI, $\Sigma cation$, and HCO_3^- to and from porewater by marine silicate alteration in 2-1_1 (Core 1) and 2-6 (Core 6) in (a) Zone 1, (b) Zone 2, and (c) Zone 3. LSi dissolution is the combined dissolution of albite, phlogopite, and vermiculite. The clay formation is the summation of saponite and montmorillonite formation. Zones are defined by the measured results of DSi/Cl^- and $\delta^{30}Si_{pw}$, as described in Section 3.2. Positive values denote net productions (i.e. release to porewater), while negative values denote consumptions (i.e. uptake from porewater). (d) Average net production or removal of DSI, $\Sigma cation$, and HCO_3^- (i.e. LSi dissolution + BSi dissolution (only for Si) – clay formation) for individual zones (Zone 1 (Z1) to Zone 3 (Z3)) and the entire core (Entire) for the two best-fit scenarios.

saturation was however observed among the five scenarios (Fig. S2). This indicates that the differences in reaction rates (see Section 4.2) are not primarily due to the degree of disequilibrium but to other factors.

3.3.2. DSi , cation, and HCO_3^- production/consumption by marine silicate alteration

The DSi , $\Sigma cation$, and HCO_3^- production/consumption by marine silicate alteration in 2-1_1 and 2-6 were calculated from scenarios *Core 1* and *Core 6*, respectively, using Equation S3 (Fig. 4). As compared to *Core 6*, scenario *Core 1* has slower DSi production by BSi dissolution as well as slower DSi , $\Sigma cation$, and HCO_3^- consumptions by clay formation for all zones (Figs. 4a, 4b, and 4c). In addition, *Core 1* has slower DSi , $\Sigma cation$, and HCO_3^- productions by LSi dissolution in Zone 1 (Fig. 4a) and faster DSi , $\Sigma cation$, and HCO_3^- productions by LSi dissolution in Zone 3 than those of *Core 6* (Fig. 4c). Similar rates of DSi , $\Sigma cation$, and HCO_3^- productions by LSi dissolution were found between two sites in Zone 2 (Fig. 4b).

For the two best-fit simulations of the two study sites (i.e. *Core 1* and *Core 6*), net consumptions of DSi , $\Sigma cation$, and HCO_3^- can be observed in Zone 1, whereas net productions of DSi , $\Sigma cation$, and HCO_3^- can be found in Zones 2 and 3 (Fig. 4d). For the entire core, both scenarios show a net removal of DSi and net productions of $\Sigma cation$ and HCO_3^- (Fig. 4d). Between the two sites our modeling predicts faster net $\Sigma cation$ and HCO_3^- productions in 2-1_1 (*Core 1*) than those in 2-6 (*Core 6*) (Fig. 4d).

4. Discussion

4.1. Dominant mica group silicate dissolution inferred from $\delta^{30}Si$ values and elemental composition of reactive LSi phase

LSi dissolution has been emphasized in a few recent studies for its capability to affect subsurface major cation and alkalinity budgets (Kim et al., 2016; Torres et al., 2020; Wallmann et al., 2023). Based on the downcore enrichment of Na^+ , K^+ , and Mg^{2+} in porewater and the depletion of Na, Ca, and Mg in bulk sediment, Wallmann et al. (2008) suggested that igneous minerals (plagioclase, feldspar, and olivine) are the main dissolving silicate phases in marine sediments from the central Sea of Okhotsk. Multiple studies (Vorhies and Gaines, 2009; Liu et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2019; Köster et al., 2021; Jung et al., 2022) found evidence of clay minerals dissolution (illite, smectite, and illite-smectite) induced by microbial respiration in marine sediment. Meister et al. (2022) applied reactive transport modeling and found that vermiculite and chlorite are undersaturated and able to release K^+ and Mg^{2+} under a general porewater geochemical composition.

The high porewater TA from our study sites in the Ulleung Basin indicates prevailing LSi dissolution and net marine silicate weathering. Kim et al. (2016) reported high radiogenic strontium isotopic values ($^{87}Sr/^{86}Sr$) and K^+ concentrations in porewater and attributed these geochemical signatures to the dissolution of K-bearing silicates, such as K-feldspar or mica minerals. The elemental and isotopic compositions from our sequential leaching results support the inference of K-bearing silicate weathering. It has been suggested that Si, Al, and K can be congruently released during alkaline leaching of K-feldspar (Alekseyev et al., 1997) and illite (Köhler et al., 2003; Smith et al., 2017). The Si/K, Si/Al, and K/Al ratios of the reactive LSi phase are close to the measured stoichiometric values of mica group silicates (including primary mica and secondary illite or illite-smectite mixed layer silicates) rather than K-feldspar (Figs. 5, S1b, and S1d) (Song and Huang, 1988; Chuhan et al., 2000). Si isotopic compositions of the reactive LSi phase agree with the literature values from illite or smectite-rich sediments (-1.2 to -0.1 ‰; Bayon et al., 2018) and primary mica (-0.5 to 0 ‰; Georg, 2006) (Fig. 5). We also showed previously that the content of mica group minerals in our leached sediments was reduced after the entire leaching, potentially due to the NaOH treatment (Huang et al., 2023). Our modeling of silicate mineral saturation provides further confirmation by suggesting that phlogopite and its weathered secondary phases,

Fig. 5. The plot of Si isotopic composition vs. Si/K in the reactive LSi phase. Black rectangle represents ranges of values for K-feldspar (Song and Huang, 1988; Chuhan et al., 2000; Savage et al., 2012). Red and orange rectangles represent ranges of values for primary mica (e.g. muscovite and biotite) (Pal, 1985; Holdaway et al., 1988; Georg, 2006) and secondary mica (e.g. illite and illite-smectite) (Lynch, 1997; Bayon et al., 2018). Our leachate data from the two study sites mostly fall in the range for secondary mica group silicates. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

vermiculite, are undersaturated in the observed porewater composition, while microcline, saponite, and montmorillonite are oversaturated (Fig. S2). The dissolution of phlogopite and/or vermiculite explains the high porewater Mg^{2+} and K^+ concentrations, as suggested by our best-fit scenarios *Core 1* and *Core 6* (Fig. 3). Biotite flakes, one type of K- and Mg-rich mica, have been identified in laminated mud and tephra layers within the Ulleung Basin sediments (Bahk et al., 2000; Park et al., 2003), likely sourced either from Chinese river discharge transported via the Tsushima Warm Current or from volcanic events (Hong et al., 1997; Um et al., 2017). Collectively, we conclude that the dissolution of mica group silicates that are enriched in K and Mg is primarily responsible for the high TA in porewater from both studied sites. A global compilation by Hong et al. (2025) showed that porewater Mg^{2+} concentrations exceeding seawater levels were observed at the majority of sites with elevated TA (> 56 meq L^{-1}), and Mg^{2+} accounted for about 40 % of the measured TA. These observations highlight the potentially crucial role of K- and Mg-rich mica delivery to marine sediments in promoting net marine silicate weathering.

4.2. Rate of marine silicate alteration controlled by biogeochemical processes in the Ulleung Basin

Dissolution of K- and Mg-rich mica group silicates is not always the most dominant marine silicate alteration process in the three early diagenetic zones. This is evident, for example, from the decreasing porewater Mg^{2+} concentrations in Zone 3 (Figs. 2d and 2h) that indicate a transition from silicate dissolution to clay formation. Below, we discuss the key microbial processes that determine the pathway and rates of marine silicate alteration between the two study sites and across the depth profiles based on our model-derived rate and porewater solute results (Figs. 6 and 7). The microbial network in our model is structured as follows: organic matter hydrolysis process breaks down organic matter from biopolymers into monomeric glucose (Table 1) (Hoppe, 1983, 1991). Under anoxic conditions, glucose is further decomposed

Fig. 6. (a) Profiles of porewater solute concentrations (DSi, DAL, and SO_4^{2-}), pH, TA, as well as reaction rates of hydrogenotrophic sulfate reduction (hySR), anaerobic oxidation of methane (AOM) and fermentation in model scenarios *Core 1*, *Core 1_{low org}*, and *Core 1_{low org} + CH₄*. Measurements from 2-1_1 were plotted as solid black dots for comparison. (b) Rates of Si and Σ cation production/consumption for LSi dissolution, BSi dissolution, and clay formation in scenarios *Core 1*. For clarity, only the rate differences between *Core 1_{low org}* and *Core 1*, as well as *Core 1_{low org} + CH₄* and *Core 1*, were shown. The depth range of the three zones was defined based on the measured $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ values and DSi/Cl⁻ ratios in 2-1_1, as discussed in Section 3.2. Sulfate-methane transition zones (SMTZ) are marked based on the modeled sulfate profiles in each scenario.

into acetate and released H^+ , hydrogen, and CO_2 through fermentation (Table 1) (Sawyer and King, 1993). The release of acetate and hydrogen fuels sulfate reduction and methanogenesis, with both processes occurring via hydrogenotrophic and acetotrophic pathways (Table 1) (Sørensen et al., 1981; King, 1984; Canfield et al., 2005). Anaerobic oxidation of methane consumes methane produced by methanogenesis and produces hydrogen and CO_2 (Table 1) (Hoehler et al., 1994; Alperin and Hoehler, 2009). We include model-derived DAL in the following discussion, as its concentration is primarily controlled by mineral reactions, despite our porewater total Al data not being able to verify the DAL results from modeling (Section 2.3).

4.2.1. Zone 1: Net reverse weathering in the sulfate reduction zone

Abrupt increases in the rates of BSi and LSi dissolution, clay formation, hydrogenotrophic sulfate reduction (hySR), and anaerobic oxidation of methane (AOM) were observed around 5.5 to 9.5 mbsf for all simulated scenarios. These increases are accompanied by the increase of pH and TA and the decrease of DSi and DAL concentrations within the shallow depth range in our modeling (Figs. 6 and 7). Variations in microbial and mineral reaction rates across scenarios are driven by differences in organic matter reactivity, as reflected by the different kinetic constants assigned for scenarios and external methane supply.

Compared to the *Core 1_{low org}*, faster hySR and an earlier onset of methanogenesis in *Core 1* and *Core 1_{low org} + CH₄* are due to either higher kinetic constants of organic matter hydrolysis assigned (*Core 1*) or a higher external methane supply prescribed (*Core 1_{low org} + CH₄*) (Fig. 6a; Table 2). HCO_3^- produced by AOM and hySR (Table 1), elevates porewater pH and promotes clay formation in the sulfate-methane transition zone (SMTZ) of *Core 1* ($329 \text{ fmol Si m}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1}$ or $633 \text{ feq m}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1}$) and *Core 1_{low org} + CH₄* ($358 \text{ fmol Si m}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1}$ or $695 \text{ feq m}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1}$) compared to those of *Core 1_{low org}* ($275 \text{ fmol Si m}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1}$ or $519 \text{ feq m}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1}$) increases DSi and DAL uptake. Lower DSi and DAL concentrations then drive the faster BSi and LSi dissolution (Fig. 6a; Table 2).

A similar inference regarding the impact of organic matter hydrolysis on net reverse weathering can be made when comparing the results from *Core 1* with those from *Core 6* and *Core 6_{kmica}*. Slower AOM and hySR in both *Core 6* and *Core 6_{kmica}* than those in *Core 1* can be attributed to lower kinetic constants for organic matter hydrolysis assigned (Fig. 7a; Table 2). This results in slower clay formation in *Core 6* and *Core 6_{kmica}*, as reflected by the negative $\Delta\text{Clay-Si}$ values across SMTZ in Fig. 7b. Slower clay formation in *Core 6* and *Core 6_{kmica}* also eases the demand for DSi and DAL, which consequently decreases BSi and LSi dissolution rates across SMTZ as compared to that of *Core 1* (Figs. 6 and 7).

Fig. 7. (a) Profiles of porewater solute concentrations (DSi, DAL and SO_4^{2-}), pH, TA, as well as reaction rates of hydrogenotrophic sulfate reduction (hySR), anaerobic oxidation of methane (AOM) and fermentation in model scenarios *Core 1*, *Core 6*, and *Core 6_{kmica}*. Measurements from 2-6 were plotted as solid black dots for comparison. (b) Rates of Si and Σ cation production/consumption for LSi dissolution, BSi dissolution and clay formation in scenarios *Core 1*. For clarity, only the rate differences between *Core 6* and *Core 1*, as well as *Core 6_{kmica}* and *Core 1*, were shown. The depth range of the three zones was defined based on the measured $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ values and DSi/ Cl^- ratios in 2-1_1, as discussed in Section 3.2. Sulfate-methane transition zones (SMTZ) are marked based on the modeled sulfate profiles in each scenario.

4.2.2. Zone 2: Net marine silicate weathering in the shallow methanogenesis zone

Below the SMTZ, our modeling fits the downcore porewater profiles with a slower clay formation compared to LSi and BSi dissolution (Figs. 6b and 7b). DSi is released through LSi dissolution at rates that are ca. 3 and 2 times faster than BSi dissolution rates for *Core 1* and *Core 6*, respectively. Cation release via LSi dissolution is ca. 8 and 5 % faster than cation uptake through clay formation for *Core 1* and *Core 6*, respectively (Figs. 6b and 7b). This suggests a dominant dissolution of LSi (represented by mica group silicates) within this zone. The dominant LSi dissolution results in net marine silicate weathering and increases downcore levels of TA, as well as cations (DAL, K^+ , and Mg^{2+}) which were observed both in modeling (Figs. 6a and 7a) and measured porewater profiles (Figs. 2a, 2d, 2e, and 2h). The increases in DAL with depth have an impact on marine silicate alteration in Zone 3 (see Section 4.2.3).

The net marine silicate weathering found in this zone is attributed to the acidified porewater due to fermentation (Table 1). *Core 1*, with the largest kinetic constant of organic matter hydrolysis (Table 2), has the lowest clay formation rate and the highest LSi dissolution rate as compared to those in other scenarios (Figs. 6b and 7b). The fastest organic matter hydrolysis and fermentation in *Core 1* produce the

highest amounts of acidity and thus suppress clay formation while promoting LSi dissolution the most (Figs. 6 and 7). The combined effect of slow clay formation and fast LSi dissolution as well as organic matter hydrolysis results in the highest DAL concentration in *Core 1* compared to other scenarios (Figs. 6a and 7a). The higher TA and cation concentrations (K^+ and Mg^{2+}) observed in 2-1_1, as compared to those in 2-6 (Fig. 2), can therefore be attributed to the more predominant LSi dissolution and suppressed clay formation in 2-1_1. (Fig. 7b). No noticeable difference in DSi concentration was observed between scenarios (Figs. 6 and 7) and measurements (Figs. 2a and 2e), as DSi concentration is buffered by BSi dissolution. Higher BSi dissolution rates in *Core 1_{low org}*, *Core 1_{low org} + CH₄*, *Core 6*, and *Core 6_{kmica}* compensate for the faster DSi removal by clay formation as compared to *Core 1* (Figs. 6b and 7b).

4.2.3. Zone 3: Waning of net silicate weathering due to the accumulation of porewater DAL in the deep methanogenesis zone

The accumulation of fermentation products, including H^+ , in Zone 3 suppresses clay formation as predicted by our modeling (Figs. 6b and 7b). With less efficient clay formation, DSi, and DAL concentrations increase with depth, which makes LSi dissolution less favourable and decreases the net silicate weathering rate (Figs. 6 and 7). Such a model-

predicted waning of net silicate weathering in Zone 3, despite the dropping pH, is supported by the decreasing TA below 150 mbsf from the measured profiles of 2-1_1 and 2-6 (Fig. 2). Our results highlight the potential role of DAL (especially labile Al^{3+}) in controlling the extent of marine silicate alteration processes across the different early diagenetic zones. DAL concentrations not only affect the solubility of BSi, as suggested by previous studies (Van Bennekom et al., 1991; Van Cappellen and Qiu, 1997; Dixit et al., 2001) but also the stability of LSi. Accurate quantification of porewater DAL concentrations are therefore important for a better constraint of marine silicate alteration. Similar decreases in TA and Mg^{2+} concentrations with depth were observed in the Central Chilean continental margin at several hundred mbsf, attributed to dominant smectite formation due to elevated temperatures (ca. 20 °C) (Scholz et al., 2013). This mechanism is likely of limited importance in our case, as comparable temperatures (20 °C) are only reached at depths of ca. 200 mbsf at both sites (Lee et al., 2013).

4.3. Contributions and controls of marine silicate alteration to porewater DSi and alkalinity in marine sediments

Net DSi consumption in Zone 1 and production in Zones 2 and 3 were calculated based on the results of Core 1 and Core 6 (Fig. 4d). It becomes apparent that DSi diffusion from Zones 2 and 3 alone cannot sustain the calculated fast DSi consumption in Zone 1 (Fig. 4d). The assigned upper boundary of high DSi concentrations in our model (868 and 749 μM for 2-1_1 and 2-6, respectively) is required to account for the observed high level of DSi in the porewater (602 to 1165 μM) and the modeled consumption in Zone 1. These upper boundaries of DSi concentrations are much higher than those of average seawater (70 μM ; Tréguer et al., 1995) and bottom seawater in the East/Japan Sea (81 to 83 μM ; Isshiki et al., 1991). Potentially, this can be explained by the asymptotic increase in downcore DSi concentrations as a result of rapid BSi dissolution in the shallow sediments (McManus et al., 1995; Dixit et al., 2001) that were not recovered by drilling.

The ability to increase alkalinity through LSi dissolution, or marine silicate weathering, has been demonstrated previously (Wallmann et al., 2008, 2023; Torres et al., 2020). Even though our modeling supports such a general conclusion, a detailed examination of our modeling results reveals critical nuances about how the coupling between LSi dissolution and clay formation affects overall alkalinity production in porewater. Raising the kinetic constants of organic matter hydrolysis by a factor of 2.2 (Table 2), the model calculated two times faster net alkalinity (and Σcation) production for Core 1 as compared to that in Core 6 (Fig. 4d) and explains the higher TA found in 2-1_1 as compared to 2-6 (Figs. 2a and 2e). However, the model predicts only a 0.5 % difference in alkalinity production from LSi dissolution between the two sites, while CO_2 production rate (or alkalinity consumption) via clay formation predicted by the model is approximately 4 % higher in Core 6 than in Core 1 (Figs. 4a, 4b, and 4c). In other words, the higher TA measured from 2-1_1 is interpreted by our modeling mostly as a result of slower clay formation rather than faster LSi dissolution in 2-1_1. In Core 1, rapid fermentation lowers pH and inhibits clay formation significantly. As a result, CO_2 production is greatly reduced in Core 1, resulting in greater net alkalinity production as compared to that in Core 6. This finding is critical for two reasons. Firstly, in contrast to the dominant role of LSi dissolution, as previously concluded (Wallmann et al., 2008, 2023; Torres et al., 2020), our finding emphasizes the role of clay formation in regulating porewater alkalinity production even in conditions favoring net marine silicate weathering. Secondly, our results also demonstrate the higher pH sensitivity of clay formation as compared to LSi dissolution. As a result, the rate of alkalinity consumption through clay formation, or reverse weathering, fluctuates among different early diagenetic zones where porewater pH is modified by the various microbial processes.

The link between microbial processes and alkalinity production becomes more evident when considering the role of organic matter

degradation (i.e. organic matter hydrolysis and fermentation). Even though organic matter degradation alone cannot explain the high TA observed from the Ulleung Basin and elsewhere (Wallmann et al., 2008; Meister et al., 2022), our results from the model sensitivity tests show that TA level depends on kinetic constants of organic matter hydrolysis, and thus the reactivity of organic matter, as long as there is sufficient mica group silicates in the sediments available for marine silicate weathering (Section 4.2.2). H^+ and CO_2 produced during organic matter degradation play crucial roles in the observed dependency of TA levels: H^+ drives the dissolution of mica group silicates, while the produced CO_2 is converted into carbonate alkalinity. The production of H^+ and CO_2 is always coupled when organic matter degradation is the primary reaction involved. However, the situation could be different when, for example, pyrite oxidation (or pyrite weathering) is the primary reaction for acidity generation (Torres et al., 2014). In this case, the production of H^+ and CO_2 may be decoupled. How marine silicate alteration responds under such a circumstance is currently unknown.

In the Ulleung Basin, rapid organic matter degradation is sustained by high primary production and the lateral transport of labile organic matter (Yoo and Park, 2009; Kim et al., 2017). Furthermore, Lee et al. (2019) reported that the organic matter oxidation rate and C/N ratio in surface sediment of the Ulleung Basin are positively correlated with water depth due to the downslope transport of labile organic matter that undergoes progressive degradation into refractory material before settling in the basin. This finding seems to explain why 2-1_1, located on the slope, exhibits higher TA than 2-6 in the basin (Fig. 1). A similar conclusion was made by Scholz et al. (2013) from the Central Chilean continental margin, where the transport/burial of labile organic matter is crucial to initiate marine silicate weathering below the sulfate reduction zone in the sediments.

4.4. Dominance of marine silicate alteration indicated by $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ and DSi

Variations in the dominance of marine silicate alteration driven by microbial processes and DAL accumulation can be inferred from down-core changes in DSi/Cl^- and $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$, as we discussed in Section 3.2. The $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ is sensitive to infer the different marine silicate alteration pathways, even though DSi concentrations are very often buffered by BSi dissolution. The decrease in $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ in Zone 2 can be attributed to predominant LSi dissolution that releases light Si isotope ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{LSi}}$: -0.7 ± 0.2 ‰) (Fig. 8a). The increases in $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ in Zones 1 and 3 are potentially the results of either BSi dissolution releasing heavy Si isotope ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{BSi}}$: 1.5 ± 0.2 ‰) and/or clay formation preferentially removing light Si isotope from the porewater (Fig. 8a) (Delstanche et al., 2009; Opfergelt et al., 2009; Oelze et al., 2014, 2015; Ehlert et al., 2016). Results from previous studies also showed that BSi dissolution and/or clay formation indeed result in higher $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ values (Fig. 8b) (-0.1 to 2.3 ‰; Ehlert et al., 2016; Cassarino et al., 2020; Ng et al., 2020; Geilert et al., 2020; Closset et al., 2022; Ward et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2024) as compared to the $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ values associated with LSi dissolution (Fig. 8b) (-0.6 to 0.3 ‰; Geilert et al., 2020; Ward et al., 2022). An exception is observed in Mariana Trench, where the predominant dissolution of ^{30}Si -depleted diatom *Ethmodiscus rex* ($\delta^{30}\text{Si}$: -1.0 ± 0.2 ‰) results in the low values of $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ (down to -0.7 ‰) (Luo et al., 2022). Notably, the compiled dataset indicates that only a few cases are significantly influenced by LSi dissolution (Fig. 8b). This is likely because most samples were collected from shallow sediment depths (< 1 mbsf), where BSi dissolution (occurring at top ca. 50 cm) and clay formation (within the sulfate reduction zone) dominate the marine silicate alteration.

Overall, our findings show that the downcore variance in marine silicate alteration in the sites with extremely high porewater TA can be revealed by measurements of $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ and DSi concentrations (red labels in Fig. 9). The decreases in $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{\text{pw}}$ in shallow methanogenesis are affected by the net marine silicate weathering of mica group silicate, with the support from $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ and elemental ratios of reactive LSi isolated from sequential leaching (purple texts in Fig. 9). Reactive transport

Fig. 9. Conceptual model illustrating marine silicate alteration in the Ulleung Basin indicated by variations in $\delta^{30}\text{Si}_{pw}$ and DSi concentrations (red labels). The type of LSi reactant is suggested based on $\delta^{30}\text{Si}$ and elemental ratios of reactive LSi isolated from sequential leaching (purple texts). The microbial process driving marine silicate alteration is inferred through reactive transport modeling (green texts). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

observed porewater profiles of the two studied sites. Our modeling reveals that changes in porewater pH resulting from microbial reactions and the concentration of DAL control the saturation of silicate minerals and their dissolution/formation rates across different diagenetic zones. We also propose an alternative explanation for how organic matter degradation promotes net marine silicate weathering: the suppression of clay formation (reverse weathering) controls the level of porewater TA in the shallow methanogenesis zone, where net marine silicate weathering occurs. This contrasting conclusion, compared to earlier hypotheses, arises from the higher pH sensitivity of clay formation. Lastly, even though porewater DSi concentrations are primarily buffered by BSi dissolution, the stable Si isotopic signature of DSi in porewater is sensitive to the different marine silicate alteration pathways.

Data Availability

Data are available through Mendeley Data at <https://doi.org/10.17632/y26yh76ww9.1>.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Tzu-Hao Huang: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Xiaole Sun:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Supervision. **Ji-Hoon Kim:** Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Chris Mark:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Wei-Li Hong:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Supervision, Methodology.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

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